

The Effect of Reading Shadowing on Iranian Elementary EFL Learners' Grammar Achievement

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ABSTRACT

The present study investigated the effects of shadowing on grammar achievement of Iranian elementary learners. To attain the purpose of the study, 40 Iranian elementary female learners of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) students were selected. They were 12 to 16 years old. The participants were assigned to two experimental groups, reading-based shadowing group and a control group. During the treatment period, the control group underwent traditional instruction. However, the experimental groups were instructed using shadowing. The results revealed that reading based had a significant effect on learners' grammar achievement. The findings are applicable in pedagogy context as well as for further research.

Keywords: Reading, Shadowing, Iranian Elementary, Grammar

Introduction

Most of the EFL teachers use traditional methods to teach grammar based on their experience and some textbooks to teach the structural points to the learners, mostly teachers used the inductive or deductive techniques in their educational contexts to apply those techniques in grammar teaching. In traditional methods to teach grammar, the grammar rules were taught and tested using the translation of sentences and textbooks and in such contexts most of the instructors ignored the role of learners in language learning. However, it seems that teaching grammar using traditional methods have been refreshed and the instructors are eager to use new techniques to teach grammar rules that emphasize the learners' roles in learning [1]. Since the students are active in shadowing technique, it can motivate them to be more interested and also may make them satisfied to continue language learning. As in shadowing practice the learners have to repeat the sentences after the instructors, the lessons can remain in their mind longer and the learners can remember the sentences immediately and readily.

Debata [2] believed that “Grammar is the study of words and the ways words work together; an invisible force that guides us as we put words together into sentences” (p.65). Any individual who communicates via a language, consciously or unconsciously is cognizant of the grammar of that language. Grammar is a significant part of the spoken and written language. Richards [3] believe that the grammar of a language is a delineation of the ways to use structures of language to transfer the meaning, so without grammar learning, it is not possible to use it effectively.

There are different ways to help EFL learners to learn different parts of language. The role of EFL teachers in this regard could not be ignored. In the process of learning a foreign language, similar to the first language, the learners need someone and some methods to imitate to learn new materials and different teachers have tried different approaches of and techniques so far. Shadowing, as an example, is a language learning technique. This technique means “learners attempt to repeat--to ‘shadow’ -- what they hear as quickly and accurately as they hear it” [4]. Ye [5] believes that in the shadowing technique, the learners need to speak while listening and they should try to keep up with the speed of the recording, almost making the sounds at the same time. Lambert [6] asserts that “shadowing exercise technically is a rhythmic acoustic tracking task that requires the practicer to make instant sounds to the sound stimulus signal” (p.590).

Therefore, as grammar teaching and learning is important in language courses and as it is necessary to test new ways to teach it, this study has been conducted. With regard to the inadequate studies on using shadowing to improve grammar, the researcher decided to study the effect of using shadowing on grammar learning.

The aim of this study is to help the teacher to find new ways to teach grammar implicitly in EFL classes. The results of this research could essentially provide insights into the improvement of Iranian EFL Learners language proficiency. It is expected that the obtained results from this research give some recommendation about the improvement of EFL learners' grammatical competence. The future researchers can use these results to make their educational contexts more interactive and interesting.

To explore the importance of shadowing in language learning the main aim of the present study was to investigate the influence of reading based on Iranian elementary EFL learners' grammar achievement.

Methodology

This study was conducted in true-experimental mode since the participants were randomly assigned to different groups. The independent variable of this study is shadowing, and the dependent variable of the study is grammar learning.

Participants

The participants of this study were 40 elementary EFL learners. The participants were females learning English as a foreign language in a language institute, aged 12-16. The researcher used the available sampling method in this study. They were randomly assigned to two groups, experimental and control group.

Instruments

There was an instrument in the present study:

Test of Grammar

The next instrument of the present study was a pretest and posttest of grammar knowledge. It was a researcher made test that included 35 multiple-choice tests. This test contained multiple-choice tests on verbs (simple present and present continuous). The criterion for the scoring procedure was one mark for each correct answer. The reliability of this test was estimated using Kr-21 formula and it was 0.85. To insure the content validity of this test, the researchers asked some experts to insure the content validity of this test. The test was administered to all of the participants to measure their knowledge of English grammar. After the treatment, this test was given to the participants as the posttest to determine the effect of treatment on the participants of the experimental groups.

Procedure

This study lasted for ten weeks. To conduct this study, the researcher chose sixty Iranian elementary learners and assigned them into two different groups. At the first session and to measure learners' grammar knowledge, the researcher used a grammar test as the pre-test. The results of the pretests revealed that at the beginning of the study, the participants of all of the groups were at the same level of proficiency in grammar knowledge. The first group was a control group, the second group was experimental group (reading -based group). The reading-based group received reading-based shadowing. The reading-based shadowing group, the researcher presented the texts in written sentences. The researcher gave some printed text to the learners which included examples of target language grammar and asked them to repeat the sentences aloud. At the end of the treatment phase and to investigate the effect of treatment, the researcher used the grammar test again as posttest. The results of pre-tests and posttests were compared to find the effect of the treatment on the experimental group.

Data Analysis

To analyze the obtained data from the grammar test and to assess the effect of treatment on the participants of the experimental groups, a set of descriptive and inferential statistics have been performed. To assess the normality of the data of pretests and posttests, One-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnow Test was performed. The researcher used ANCOVA test to compare the results of the pretests and posttests. All of the stages of data analysis have been done using SPSS 21.00.

Results

Examining the Normality of Data

Before performing the analysis of data, normality of collected data was assessed using One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test. This test was used to show the normality of distribution of data and to make decision about using parametric or nonparametric test to analyze data. In this statistics test, when significance is less than 0.05, the distribution of data is not normal and it is not possible to use parametric tests. When significance is more than 0.05, the distribution of data is normal and it is possible to use parametric tests. The results of this test are reported in Table 1.

Table 1

One-Sample Kolmogorov- Smirnow Test of Pretests and Posttests of Grammar

Test

			Grammar pretest	Grammar posttest
N			40	40
Normal Parameters ^a				
Mean			12.816	21.150
Std. Deviation			4.738	8.106
Most Differences	Extreme	Absolute	.133	.131
		Positive	.133	.088
		Negative	-.130	-.131
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z			1.027	1.018
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)			.242	.251
a. Test distribution is Normal.				

Table 1 shows the results of One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnow Test of pretests and posttests of grammar test. The results showed that the data of all of the tests are normal, because for all of the variables significance was more than 0.05. Accordingly, it was possible to use parametric tests to analyze data.

Addressing the Research Question

The research question was: Does reading-based shadowing significantly improve Iranian elementary EFL learners' grammar achievement?

At the beginning of the study and to clarify the initial level of knowledge of grammar of the participants of the control group and the reading based group, a pretest of grammar was performed. Moreover, at the end of the study a posttest of grammar was performed to show the effect of treatment on the grammar of the experimental group.

At the first stage of data analysis to answer the first research question, a set of descriptive statistics has been performed and the results of this test are reported in Table 2.

Table 2
Descriptive Statistics of Pretests of Grammar of Experimental and Control Groups

	group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Grammar Pretest	control	20	12.85	5.25	1.174
Reading group	experimental	20	12.50	4.85	1.084

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics of pretest of grammar of reading based experimental group and control groups. As it is clear from this Table, the mean scores of pretests of grammar in control and experimental groups are 12.85 and 12.50 respectively. The Std. Deviation of pretests of grammar in control and experimental groups are 5.25 and 4.85 respectively. It is clear that there is not any significant difference between the mean scores in pretests. The next table shows the mean scores of posttests of grammar of the reading based shadowing group.

Table 3
Descriptive Statistics of Posttests of Grammar of Experimental and Control Groups

groups	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Control group	13.10	5.00	20
Reading based experimental group	22.45	6.10	20
Total	17.77	7.26	40

As it is clear from the above table, the mean score of pretest of grammar test of the control and reading based experimental group are 13.10 and 22.45, respectively. According to the above table, the mean scores of reading based

experimental group in posttest were higher than the mean scores of posttest of control group. It shows that after treatment, the participants of the reading based experimental group had better performance in grammar test than the control group.

The next table shows the results of ANCOVA test of the reading based experimental group and control group in the test of grammar. This test was performed to compare the mean scores of posttests to measure the effect of treatment on grammar achievement of the participants of the reading based experimental group.

Table 4

ANCOVA Test of Mean Scores of Grammar of Reading Based Experimental and Control Groups

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta Noncent. Parameter	Observed Power ^b
Corrected Model	1624.5	2	812.2	69.1	.000	.789	138.3	1.000
Intercept	231.3	1	231.3	19.7	.000	.347	19.7	.991
Grammar Pretest reading	750.3	1	750.3	63.9	.000	.633	63.9	1.000
Based-group	931.5	1	931.5	79.3	.000	.682	79.3	1.000
Error	434.4	37	11.7					
Total	14697.0	40						
Corrected Total	2058.9	39						

As it is clear from Table 4, the Significance is less than 0.05 (i.e., 0.00). According to the results of this test, there is a significant difference between the mean scores of posttest of grammar in control and reading based experimental groups. The results of this test indicated that the mean scores of experimental group were higher than the mean scores of the control group. It showed that the participants of experimental group had better performance in the grammar test than the control group. To find out whether this difference is statistically difference, with the assumption of homogeneity of variances, pairwise comparison using Bonferroni test was made between the two groups. The results of this test are reported in the next table.

Table 5

Pairwise Comparison of the Reading Based Experimental and Control Group

(I) group	(J) group	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^a	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^a	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
control	experimental	-9.658*	1.084	.000	-11.854	-7.461
experimental	control	9.658*	1.084	.000	7.461	11.854

*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.

According to the above table, the mean difference of the reading based experimental group and the control group is -9.658. It shows that the mean scores of the reading based experimental group were significantly higher than the control group.

Conclusion

No study has been done on the effect of shadowing on grammar achievement but some researchers conducted studies on the effect of shadowing on learners' different skills and different aspects of language learning and the results of their studies are in line with the results of the present research. In this regard, the results of the present study were in line with Hamada [7, 8], Yonezava and Ware [9], Sumarish [10]. These researchers concluded that using shadowing has a significant effect on learners' listening skill. The findings of this research also in tandem with Wang [4], Omar and Umehara [11], Yavari and Shafiee [12], Azimi and Ghanbari [13], and Zakari [14] who found out that using shadowing has a significant effect on learners' speaking and oral performance. The results are also correlate with Hamada [15], Nakanishi and Ueda [16], Suzuki [17], Shiki, Mori, Kadota, and Yoshida [18], and Willardson [19]. They studied the effect of shadowing on language proficiency and the results of their study indicated the significant effect of shadowing on students' language proficiency.

It is a very long time that EFL teachers are looking for effective ways to help their students to achieve grammar easily. Shadowing has been used as a tool for language learning. In most of the language classes, teachers use traditional and explicit ways to teach grammar. Shadowing, however, is a well-established activity which is somewhat different from the traditional methods that teachers use in the classes .

The results of this study demonstrated the usefulness of shadowing for grammar learning. Based on the data analysis in the previous chapter and result and

discussions of this research, the researcher has concluded several points as follow. The results indicated that elementary learners' grammar learning improves after they have been used shadowing technique. It was proven by the data shown. The mean or the average score of grammar posttest of the participants of the reading based and listening based experimental group were higher than those of the control group and the students of the experimental groups got a better result in grammar test. This finding implies that using shadowing is a good way to help learners to improve their grammar knowledge. Therefore, it seems that using shadowing is a good approach to help learners to learn grammar and consequently improve their language proficiency level.

The results also showed that the participants of the listening based shadowing group had better performance than the participants of the reading based group. The findings indicated that there is a significant difference between the scores of the participants of reading based and listening based group and the participants of the listening based group outperformed the participants of the reading based group.

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